

Supplementary Figure S5: Significantly enriched bacterial taxa (species level) in root Preak Sdei samples (Wilcoxon test, bonferroni correction, $\alpha=5\%$).

Supplementary Figure S5:
Significantly enriched
bacterial taxa (species
level) in rhizosphere
Rovieng samples
(Wilcoxon test,
bonferroni correction,
 $\alpha=5\%$).